

Impact of Temperature on the Structural, Morphological, Magnetic, and Electrochemical Properties of Manganese Ferrite Nanoparticles Prepared by Co-Precipitation Method

K. J. Oviya, P. Sivagurunathan*

Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar, Chidambaram – 608 002, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract— MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully synthesized through a simple co-precipitation technique. TG-DTA analysis of the prepared nanoparticles revealed thermal stability above 390 °C. Subsequently, the synthesized nanoparticles underwent calcination at various temperatures like 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C and these samples were subjected to characterizations such as XRD, FTIR, and VSM. For further characterization, the MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles calcinated at 600 °C were specifically examined by FESEM coupled with EDX, HRTEM with SAED, and CV analysis. The X-ray diffraction analysis provided the structural information, indicating the presence of a cubic spinel structure with Fd3m space group and the crystallite size increased linearly with calcination temperature. In the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, characteristic absorption bands identified around 562 cm⁻¹ and 434 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the vibrations of tetrahedral and octahedral complexes of manganese ferrite nanoparticles, respectively. The surface morphology of the MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles, as observed through field emission scanning electron microscope images, displayed a spherical shape with slight agglomeration. The EDX analysis indicated the existence of O, Fe, and Mn elements without any impurities. HRTEM micrographs further revealed the spherical shape of the nanoparticles with little agglomeration. The average crystallite size calculated using Debye-Scherrer's formula is in good agreement with HRTEM analysis. The magnetic measurements of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles performed by VSM exhibit enhanced magnetization and coercivity values for different calcination temperatures which shows the soft ferrimagnetic behavior and is suitable for magnetic storage devices. The electrochemical characteristics of manganese ferrite nanoparticles were examined using CV analysis. Notably, a specific capacitance of 390 F/g was recorded at a scan rate of 2 mV/s for MnFe₂O₄ signifies the exceptional quality of these nanoparticles and their potential suitability for supercapacitor applications.

Keywords— Manganese ferrite, XRD, FTIR, FESEM, HRTEM, VSM and CV

I. Introduction

The rapid growth of global population and industrial activity is driving a substantial increase in energy demand [1]. As fossil fuels are the predominant source of energy, their rapid consumption is leading to the depletion of resources [2]. To address this challenge, it is essential to advance and adopt more sustainable and efficient energy storage and conversion technologies [3]. In this context, nanostructures and nanomaterials with their unique

nanoscale characteristics, have the potential to revolutionize energy storage solutions and help reduce our reliance on diminishing fossil fuels [4, 5]. Magnetic nanoparticles, in particular, have shown great potential due to their enhanced physical and chemical properties, which vary with size and differs significantly from their bulk counterparts [6]. By integrating these advancements in nanotechnology with energy storage systems, researchers aim to fulfill the future energy requirements[7]. Ferrites are attractive magnetic materials which have a variety of applications including energy storage systems, sensors, and magnetic resonance imaging. The performance of ferrites depends significantly on their composition and microstructure, which are in turn affected by their processing conditions and method of preparation [8]. Spinel ferrite nanoparticles, denoted by the formula MFe_2O_4 (with M representing divalent ions such as Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Mg, etc.), are known for their exceptional magnetic, optical, electrical, catalytic, electrochemical, and biomedical properties [9-11]. Among all the nano spinel ferrites known today, $MnFe_2O_4$, classified as a soft spinel ferrite, exhibits notable traits including a substantial surface area, elevated magnetic permeability, considerable electrical resistance and it is widely utilized in a variety of applications, including magnetic resonance imaging, supercapacitors, gas sensors, high-density magnetic recording, and the treatment of hyperthermia, drug delivery system [12- 14]. Manganese ferrite nanoparticles can be prepared using various techniques such as co-precipitation [15], hydrothermal reaction [16], sol-gel [17], thermal decomposition [18] mechano-chemical reaction [19], ball milling [20], and auto combustion [21]. The co-precipitation process stands out as a preferred method for efficiently producing ultrafine nanoparticles with exceptional purity, crystallinity, and high yields in the shortest time [22]. This paper utilizes the co-precipitation method for synthesizing manganese ferrite nanoparticles. The synthesized nanoparticles undergo characterization via XRD, FTIR, FESEM with EDX, HRTEM, VSM, and CV analysis.

II. Experimental details

1. Materials

Manganese nitrate ($Mn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) and ferric nitrate ($Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$) obtained from Merck chemicals in pure AR grade (99%) served as the metal nitrate precursors for synthesizing $MnFe_2O_4$ nanoparticles. NaOH was employed as the precipitating agent, while distilled water served as the solvent. No further purification was carried out on the reagents prior to their use in this study.

2. Synthesis of $MnFe_2O_4$ nanoparticles

$MnFe_2O_4$ nanoparticles were synthesized using a chemical co-precipitation technique [23]. Manganese nitrate and iron nitrate were dissolved separately in 30 ml of double-distilled water in a stoichiometric ratio of 1:2, then stirred magnetically. An appropriate amount of sodium hydroxide was added to the nitrate mixture dropwise with constant stirring and the pH was maintained at 9 throughout the synthesis process. The entire solution was stirred at 60 °C for 2 hours using a magnetic stirrer until a dark brown precipitate was formed. The obtained product was washed with acetone and double distilled water several times to remove the impurities. The resultant product was dried in a hot air oven at 100 °C and then ground using agate mortar. Based on TG/DT analysis the prepared samples were calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C for 3 hours.

III. Characterization techniques

The thermal behavior of as-prepared sample was analyzed by TG/DTA using the instrument NETZSCH STA 449F3. Using Cu-K α radiation, the phases and crystalline structure of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were investigated with a PAN analytical (X' Pert-Pro) X-ray diffractometer. JCPDS database was utilized to interpret the XRD spectra. Using KBr pellet, FTIR spectra was recorded using Perkin Elmer spectrometer within the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range. The structural characteristics of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles was studied with FESEM instrument CARL ZEISS- SIGMA 300 scanning electron microscope coupled with EDX for elemental analysis. Using JEOL Japan, JEM-2100 Plus, HRTEM measurements were obtained. With VSM lakeshore 7404-S, magnetic measurements at room temperature up to 15 kOe was carried out. Cyclic voltammetric analysis was carried out by Metrohm autolab.

IV. Results and discussion

1. TG/DTA

To investigate the thermal stability and formation process of manganese ferrite nanoparticles, the synthesized MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were subjected to simultaneous thermal gravimetric and differential thermal analysis (TG/DTA) at temperatures ranging from 30 °C to 1000 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C / minute in a nitrogen gas atmosphere. Fig. 1 displays the TG/DTA curve of the as prepared product.

Fig. 1 TG/DT analysis of as-prepared MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles

The TG curve indicates that there are two distinct stages of thermal decomposition. The initial weight loss of 12% between 30 °C and 155 °C is attributed to the loss of water content present in the synthesized material. The second weight loss of 15% occurs at the temperature range 155 °C- 390 °C corresponds to the decomposition of residues like nitrates and other organic templates. No weight loss occurs beyond 390 °C attaining a stable state thereafter, which confirms the formation of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles [24]. In the DTA curve, the formation of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles is signified by two exothermic peaks at 240 °C and 385 °C, respectively. The first

exothermic peak at 240 °C is owing to the desorption of water molecules and the second exothermic peak at 385 °C is caused by the thermal decomposition of organic templates and formation of the final product [25].

2. X-ray diffraction

Fig. 2 presents the XRD patterns of both the as prepared and calcinated MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles at temperatures of 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C.

Fig. 2 XRD spectra of as-prepared and calcinated MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles

Absence of crystalline peaks in the XRD pattern of the as-prepared powder confirms its amorphous nature, emphasizing the necessity of calcination for crystallite stabilization and preventing agglomeration [26]. Upon calcination, the XRD pattern of manganese ferrite nanoparticles reveals distinct reflections corresponding to crystallographic planes with h, k, and l values of (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511), and (440). These reflections signify the formation of a single-phase cubic spinel structure, with an $Fd\bar{3}m$ space group [27]. The measured XRD peaks align closely with the characteristic peaks of the cubic phase of manganese ferrite as documented in JCPDS, File No. # 74-2403 [28]. The absence of additional peaks indicates the formation of manganese ferrite nanoparticles devoid of impurities. An increase in calcination temperature from 400 °C to 500 °C and 500 °C to 600 °C leads to a progressive increase in the peak intensity and a decrease in the peak width, indicating an improvement in the crystalline nature of the nanoparticles [29]. The present study concludes that sharp and intense peaks at 600 °C reveal a high degree of crystallinity in the synthesized MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles. The average crystallite size D can be determined using Debye-Scherrer's equation [30]

$$D = \frac{\kappa\lambda}{\beta\cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

Where, 'D' – Average crystallite size, 'K' – Scherrer constant (0.9), ' λ ' - Wavelength of X-ray (1.5406 Å), ' β ' – Full width at half maximum, ' θ ' - Diffraction angle.

The lattice parameter 'a' is estimated employing the equation [31]

$$a = d_{hkl} \sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2} \quad (2)$$

The variations in crystallite size and lattice parameter of manganese ferrite nanoparticles with different calcination temperatures are provided in Table 1.

Table 1 Structural parameters of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C

Temperature (°C)	Crystallite size (nm)	Lattice Parameter (Å)
400	14	8.346
500	17	8.361
600	20	8.375

The observed crystallite sizes are 14 nm, 17 nm, and 20 nm for 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C respectively, indicating a linear relation with crystallite size and calcination temperatures. The increase in crystallite size with an increase in calcination temperatures observed in the present study demonstrates the growth of manganese ferrite nanoparticles. This observation corresponds with the results reported by Naseri *et al.*, for the preparation of manganese ferrite nanoparticles by thermal treatment method [32]. Additionally, the lattice parameter 'a' exhibited values of 8.346 Å, 8.361 Å, and 8.375 Å for MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C respectively. The observed rise in lattice constant with increasing calcination temperature in the present work may be attributed to the microstructural changes of manganese ferrite nanoparticles [33].

3. Functional group analysis

The FTIR spectra of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles calcinated at different temperatures are recorded across the frequency ranging between 4000 cm⁻¹ and 400 cm⁻¹ as depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 FTIR spectra of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C

The most notable IR bands, found between 1000 and 400 cm^{-1} , signify the vibrations of M-O bonds. Upon calcination at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C, all functional groups within the 3600 – 1200 cm^{-1} range disappeared [34]. The current work shows two absorption bands in the spectral range of 700 - 400 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the stretching vibrations of tetrahedral and octahedral sites of manganese ferrite nanoparticles as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 The absorption band of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C and 600 °C

Temperature(°C)	MnFe_2O_4	
	$\nu_1 (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\nu_2(\text{cm}^{-1})$
400	559	431
500	562	434
600	567	438

The higher absorption band ν_1 , observed around 562 cm^{-1} , is indicative of the stretching vibrations occurring in Mn-O tetrahedral complexes, whereas the lower absorption band ν_2 , which appears around 434 cm^{-1} , is ascribed to the vibrations in Fe-O octahedral groups. These absorption bands observed in the current work represent the characteristic peaks of manganese ferrite nanoparticles [35].

4. FESEM with EDX analysis

Figure 4 (a), (b), and (c) depicts the FESEM micrographs of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles at 600 °C with different magnifications.

Fig. 4 (a), (b), (c) FESEM micrographs of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 600°C for different magnifications (d) EDX, and (e) Corresponding weight percentage

The MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles exhibit a spherical shape with nearly homogeneous characteristics, displaying a relatively uniform grain distribution. Some slight agglomeration observed at a few places might be due to higher interaction between magnetic particles [36]. The compositional analysis and the corresponding weight percentage of synthesized manganese ferrite nanoparticles identified by EDX are shown in Fig 4 (d), (e). The EDX pattern confirms the existence of O, Fe, and Mn as the primary elements in the synthesized nanomaterial [37]. The minor peaks detected in the EDX spectrum of synthesized manganese ferrite nanoparticles sample result from the presence of gold, which was applied as a coating on the synthesized samples prior to FESEM imaging to improve surface morphology visibility [38]. No other impurities are detected in this spectrum which confirms the purity of prepared manganese ferrite nanoparticles. The atomic abundance of Mn and Fe is found to be 17.12 (At%) and 30.81 (At%) indicating a close-to-stoichiometric ratio of $\sim 1:2$ (Mn: Fe) in manganese ferrite nanoparticles [39].

5. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy

Morphology of the synthesized MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles has been examined using HRTEM. Micrographs of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 600°C with various magnifications are depicted in Figure 5 (a), (b), and (c).

Fig. 5 (a), (b), (c) HRTEM micrographs of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 600°C for different magnifications (d) SAED, and (e) Corresponding histogram

The micrographs of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles revealed clear morphology of spherical form with little agglomerations [40]. The slight agglomeration observed in the manganese ferrite nanoparticles may be attributed to elevated surface energy, extensive specific surface area, and dipolar attractive forces among the magnetic nanoparticles [41]. Fig. 5 (d) showcases the SAED analysis, displaying a ring-like pattern composed of bright spots which indicates the polycrystalline nature and high crystallinity of the MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles. These observed diffraction rings correspond to the (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), and (511) crystallographic planes of the standard manganese ferrite structure obtained from XRD [42]. The histogram illustrating size distribution in Fig. 5 (e) is derived from enumerating individual particles observed in the micrographs. Utilizing "Image J viewer software," the length of the particles selected were measured and the average particle size of 24 nm observed through HRTEM is consistent with the findings from X-ray diffraction [43].

6. Magnetic property

Figure 6 displays the magnetic field dependence of the magnetization of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles subjected to calcination temperatures of 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C has been conducted using a vibrating sample magnetometer at 300K, with magnetic field ranging from -15 kOe upto 15 kOe.

Fig. 6 Room temperature M-H curves for MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C and 600 °C

From Fig. 6 it is clear that the saturation magnetization (M_s) could not be attained even at high field indicating that the prepared MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles are ferrimagnetic in nature [44]. The observed unsaturation magnetization in this study can be attributed to spin disorder at the nanoparticle surface [45]. Within spinel ferrites, metallic ions interact in three distinct ways: A-A interactions, B-B interactions, and A-B interactions. Notably, the A-B interaction tends to exert a stronger influence compared to both the A-A and B-B interactions. According to Neel's two - sub-lattice theory of ferrimagnetism, the sub-lattice magnetizations $\Sigma M_{\text{B-sites}}$ and $\Sigma M_{\text{A-sites}}$ are aligned antiparallel, and therefore, the total magnetization of the ferrite unit cell arises from their subtraction, $M_s = \Sigma M_{\text{B-sites}} - \Sigma M_{\text{A-sites}}$ [46]. The saturation magnetization value was obtained by extrapolating the inverse of the field vs. magnetization (M) plot to $1/H=0$. The saturation magnetization and coercivity values of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at different temperatures namely 400, 500, and 600 °C are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Magnetic parameters of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated temperature at 400 °C, 500 °C and 600 °C

Temperature (°C)	M_s (emu/g)	H_c (Oe)
400	17	40
500	21	52
600	27	65

The saturation magnetization values for the prepared MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles are calculated as 17, 21, and 27 emu/g at calcination temperatures of 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C, respectively [47]. The observed increase in saturation magnetization with increasing calcination temperature may be attributed to changes in ionic distribution [48]. The magnetic saturation values obtained for the manganese ferrite nanoparticle are smaller than that of the bulk manganese ferrite which is 80 emu/g [49]. The decrease in magnetization could be attributed to the spin canting and structural distortions at the surface of the nanoparticles. Furthermore, the variations in cation distribution within the manganese ferrite nanoparticles could also contribute to the lower saturation magnetization compared to bulk counterparts [50]. The coercivity values of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles calcinated at 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C are 40 Oe, 52 Oe, and 65 Oe respectively. The obtained coercivity values in this study clearly show that the synthesized manganese ferrite nanoparticles are soft ferrimagnetic in nature [51]. In the present study, the observed increase in saturation magnetization and coercivity values of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles with the rise in calcination temperatures from 400 °C to 600 °C is caused by the migration of magnetic Fe^{3+} ions from the tetrahedral site to the octahedral site. This migration displaces some non-magnetic Mn^{2+} ions to the octahedral site, thereby enhancing the concentration of Fe^{3+} magnetic ions in the octahedral site [52]. Additionally, the increase in saturation magnetization with increasing nanoparticle size as the calcination temperature rises may result from the ordering of cations at the octahedral and tetrahedral sites, which increases with temperature, along with a decrease in the surface-to-volume ratio [53]. Moreover, the increment in the saturation magnetization is due to the improvement of crystallite size and the decrease in oxygen vacancy concentration [54].

In this study, manganese ferrite nanoparticles with crystallite sizes of 14 nm, 17 nm, and 20 nm are obtained for temperatures of 400 °C, 500 °C, and 600 °C respectively. These sizes are notably below the critical size of 30 nm confirmed the single domain nature [55]. Furthermore, the present work demonstrates a linear relationship between temperature and coercivity values, indicating the single domain nature of the prepared manganese ferrite nanoparticles [56]. The higher magnetic saturation and coercivity values observed in manganese ferrite nanoparticles is due to the prominent superexchange interactions, magnetocrystalline anisotropy, and spin-canting effects, which collectively have impact on the magnetic properties. In the present work, the synthesized pure MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles exhibit high saturation magnetization and coercivity values, making them well-suited for the development of new magnetic materials.

7. Cyclic Voltammetry (CV)

Figure 7 depicts the CV curves of the manganese ferrite electrode recorded at various scan rates from 2 to 100 mV/s within the potential of 0 to 0.4 V.

Fig. 7 CV pattern of manganese ferrite nanoparticles calcinated at 600 °C at different scan rates

At a scan rate of 2 mV/s, the CV curve exhibits an ideal rectangular shape. However, with a higher scan rate, the pattern of the cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves alters, displaying redox peaks that signify the pseudo-capacitive behavior of MnFe_2O_4 nanoparticles [57]. With the increase in scan rates, there is a corresponding increase in current density, accompanied by shifts of the anodic and cathodic peaks to higher and lower potentials, respectively as shown in Fig. 7. These changes suggest the presence of a rapid and reversible Faradaic reaction occurring at the interface between the electroactive materials and the electrolyte [58].

The specific capacitance of the MnFe_2O_4 electrode can be determined using the equation [59]

$$C_s = \frac{Q}{m \cdot \Delta V} \quad (3)$$

where, C_s is the specific capacitance, Q average charge recorded during each scan, m is the mass of the active material, and Δv – difference in potential window.

Electrochemical experiments were performed using a 0.1M solution of KOH, employing a standard three-electrode configuration. This setup comprised of samples as the working electrode, an Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode, and a high platinum wire acting as the counter electrode [60]. The scan rates of 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 100 mV/s, with the respective specific capacitance values are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4 Specific capacitance values of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles calcinated at 600 °C

Scan rate (mVs ⁻¹)	2	5	10	20	30	40	50	100
Specific capacitance (Fg ⁻¹)	390	312	230	180	101	69	37	10

Furthermore, at a scan rate of 2 mV/s, the samples calcinated at 600 °C showed a specific capacitance value of 390 F/g. The elevated specific capacitance at the lower scan rate implies that the higher scan rates restrict the accessibility of ions within each pore of the electrode, resulting in solely the outermost segment of the electrode being involved in ion diffusion. The increased specific capacitance values observed in this study are attributed to the uniformly distributed spherical morphology of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles, which are interconnected, facilitating an accessible point for the charge transfer mechanism [61]. In contrast to the findings of abisha *et al.*, [62] for manganese ferrite, who reported a specific capacitance of 223 F/g at a scan rate of 5mV/s with a crystallite size of 35 nm at 700 °C, the present study observed a greater specific capacitance of 312 F/g under similar scan rates, with the crystallite size being 20 nm at 600 °C. The elevated capacitance values achieved at reduced scan rates indicate its potential suitability for use in supercapacitor applications.

IV. Conclusion

MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully synthesized through a simple co-precipitation technique. The structural, compositional, magnetic, and electrochemical characteristics of the synthesized MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles at various calcination temperatures were thoroughly investigated. TGA analysis revealed no weight loss after 390 °C and the exothermic peak at 385 °C in DTA affirmed the formation of MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. XRD examination unveiled a cubic structure of manganese ferrite nanoparticles with the space group Fd3m and the crystallite size increased linearly with calcination temperature. The FTIR spectra of the metal Fe-O and Mn-O stretching vibrations indicated that the prepared product is manganese ferrite nanoparticles. Morphological assessment through FESEM imaging illustrated the spherical nature of the manganese ferrite particles. Elemental composition analysis via EDX spectra confirmed the existence of O, Fe, and Mn in the synthesized MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. HRTEM micrographs confirmed the spherical shape of the nanoparticles. The particle size, obtained from HRTEM analysis is in good agreement with the average crystallite size calculated from XRD. The magnetic saturation and coercivity values varied with temperature demonstrated the soft ferrimagnetic behavior of the synthesized manganese ferrite nanoparticles and it is suitable for magnetic storage devices. Cyclic voltammetric analysis of the MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles revealed an enhanced capacitance value of 390 F/g at the scan rate of 2 mV/s, suggesting its potential suitability for supercapacitor applications.

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